

PLAN VIEW

SCALE 1:10

SIDE ELEVATION – PORT

SCALE 1:10

FRONT ELEVATION

SCALE 1:10

NOTES:
 1. ALL STEEL TUBE ASTM A500 GRADE B. 2. ALL WELDS MIG, ER70S-6, 3/16" FILLET MIN. 3. SEE A03 FOR FRAME DETAILS. 4. SEE A04 FOR SECTIONS A-A, B-B, C-C.

DRIVE-IN HYBRID
 DUCK BLIND
 GENERAL ARRANGEMENT

ALL VIEWS SCALE 1:10 UNLESS NOTED

KEY DIMENSIONS

COMPACT FOOTPRINT	12'-0" x 8'-0"
EXPANDED FOOTPRINT	16'-0" x 8'-0"
WALL HEIGHT	4'-0" (48")
PEAK HEIGHT	6'-0" (72")
BOAT SLOT	52" W x 10'-0" L
FRAME MATERIAL	2"x2"x0.120" A500-B
OUTRIGGERS	4x PEDESTAL, 0-120°
DROP LEGS	4x TELESCOPING, 0-24"
EST. WEIGHT	780 LBS
MAX LOAD	2,000 LBS

PORT ELEVATION

SCALE 1:10
LOOKING TO STARBOARD

STARBOARD ELEVATION

SCALE 1:10
LOOKING TO PORT

BOW ELEVATION

SCALE 1:10
LOOKING AFT

STERN ELEVATION

SCALE 1:10
LOOKING FORWARD - ENTRY END

- NOTES:
1. ALL DIMENSIONS IN INCHES UNLESS NOTED.
 2. OUTRIGGERS SHOWN DEPLOYED (SOLID GREEN) AND STOWED (DASHED GREEN).
 3. CAMO PANEL ZONES - SEE A06 FOR PANEL DETAILS, FOLD-OUT SECTIONS - SEE A05 FOR HINGE DETAILS.

DRIVE-IN HYBRID DUCK BLIND

ELEVATIONS

SHEET A02 OF 12

REV A - 2026-03-06

FRAME PLAN VIEW

SCALE 1:10

ISOMETRIC VIEW - 3/4

SCALE ~1:12 (NTS)

JOINT DETAILS

SCALE 1:2

D1
CORNER JOINT
FLOOR-TO-WALL

D2
RAFTER-TO-WALL
TOP CONNECTION

D3
OUTRIGGER PEDESTAL
MOUNTING PLATE

- NOTES:
1. ALL SQUARE TUBE ASTM A500 GRADE B, Fy=46 KSI.
 2. ALL WELDS MIG, ER70S-6, 3/16" FILLET MTN UNLESS NOTED.
 3. GUSSET PLATES A36 STEEL, PLASMA CUT, DEBURR ALL EDGES.

4. OUTRIGGER MOUNTING PLATES WELDED ALL-AROUND TO FLOOR FRAME.
5. ALL JOINTS TO BE COPED/FISH-MOUTHED FOR FLUSH FIT BEFORE WELDING.
6. SEE A01 FOR GENERAL ARRANGEMENT. SEE A04 FOR CROSS-SECTIONS.

CUT LIST - STRUCTURAL FRAME

ITEM	QTY	SIZE	LENGTH	ANGLE	MATERIAL
Floor perimeter (long)	2	2x2x0.120	144"	0deg	A500-B
Floor perimeter (short)	2	2x2x0.120	96"	0deg	A500-B
Floor cross-member (full)	2	2x2x0.120	96"	0deg	A500-B
Floor cross-member (port)	5	2x2x0.120	22"	0deg	A500-B
Floor cross-member (stbd)	5	2x2x0.120	22"	0deg	A500-B
Boat slot rail (long)	2	2x2x0.120	120"	0deg	A500-B
Wall stud (port/stbd)	12	2x2x0.120	48"	0deg	A500-B
Wall stud (end)	8	2x2x0.120	48"	0deg	A500-B
Top rail (long)	2	2x2x0.120	144"	0deg	A500-B
Top rail (short)	2	2x2x0.120	96"	0deg	A500-B
Roof rafter	6	2x2x0.120	~54"	26.6deg	A500-B
Ridge beam	1	2x2x0.120	144"	0deg	A500-B
Gusset plate	24	3/16" plate	4"x4"	45deg	A36

STEEL SUMMARY

2x2x0.120 SQ TUBE ~132 LF (11 sticks @ 20')
 3/16" A36 PLATE 24 pcs, 4"x4" (2.67 SF)
 EST. FRAME WEIGHT ~420 LBS

DRIVE-IN HYBRID DUCK BLIND
STRUCTURAL FRAME

ALL VIEWS SCALE 1:10 UNLESS NOTED

SECTION A-A

SCALE 1:5 - AT 36" FROM BOW (SOLID FLOOR ZONE)

SECTION B-B

SCALE 1:8 - AT 72" FROM BOW (MID-SPAN, THROUGH BOAT SLOT)

SECTION C-C

SCALE 1:8 - AT 108" FROM BOW (NEAR STERN / ENTRY)

ROOF FRAMING PLAN

SCALE 1:12 - LOOKING DOWN
TOP RAIL 2x2 (PORT)

- NOTES:
1. ALL SECTIONS LOOKING TOWARD BOW UNLESS NOTED.
 2. TUBE CROSS-SECTIONS SHOWN HATCHED AT CUT PLANE.
 3. BOAT SLOT OPEN IN SECTIONS B-B AND C-C; SOLID FLOOR IN SECTION A-A.
 4. GUIDE RAILS: UHMW-PE STRIP ON STEEL CHANNEL, BOTH SIDES OF SLOT.
 5. SEE A03 FOR FRAME MEMBER SIZES. SEE A05 FOR OUTRIGGER DETAILS. SEE A08 FOR DROP LEG DETAILS.
 6. ROOF PITCH: ~26.6° (12:24 RISE OVER 48" HALF-SPAN).

**DRIVE-IN HYBRID
DUCK BLIND
CROSS SECTIONS**

SECTIONS A-A, B-B, C-C PER SHEET A01

SHEET A04 OF 12

REV A - 2026-03-06

BOAT SLOT – PLAN VIEW

GUIDE RAIL CROSS-SECTION

SCALE 1:1

LONGITUDINAL SECTION – BOAT SLOT

SCALE 1:8 – LOOKING TO PORT

GUIDE RAIL ASSEMBLY

SCALE 1:1 – CROSS-SECTION DETAIL

GUIDE RAIL BOM (QTY 2)

ITEM	DESCRIPTION	QTY
1	C3x4.1 CHANNEL x 120"	2
2	UHMW-PE STRIP 3/4"x3"x120"	2
3	3/8"-16 SHCS x 1" W/ LOCKNUT	20
4	TIE-DOWN D-RING 1/2" WELDED	4

ENTRY RAMP DETAIL

SCALE 1:4 – ISOMETRIC-STYLE VIEW

DRIVE-IN HYBRID DUCK BLIND BOAT ENTRY SYSTEM

BOAT SLOT, GUIDE RAILS, UHMW BUMPERS & ENTRY RAMP

SHEET A06 OF 12

REV A – 2026-03-06

DRAWN BY:	D. HAMPSON	DATE:	2026-03-06	SCALE:	AS NOTED
MATERIAL:	STEEL (FRAME), 6061-T6 AL (RAMP)				
FINISH:	GALV (STEEL) / MILL (AL) / NATURAL (UHMW)				
WEIGHT:	~45 LB (RAILS + UHMW), ~28 LB (RAMP)				

- NOTES: TOLERANCES (UNLESS NOTED):
- BOAT SLOT OPENING: 120" LONG, 36" WIDE, CENTERED IN FLOOR FRAME.
 - GUIDE RAILS: 120" LONG, 3" HIGH, WITH 3" UHMW-PE BUMPER STRIP, FULL LENGTH.
 - UHMW-PE: ULTRA-HIGH MOLECULAR WEIGHT POLYETHYLENE, NATURAL COLOR.
 - D-RINGS: 1/2" WELDED AT 4 CORNERS, 12" INSET FROM SLOT ENDS, 3" FROM EDGES.
 - ENTRY RAMP: 3/16" 6061-T6 DIAMOND PLATE, PIANO HINGE TO FLOOR FRAME.
 - RAMP STOWS VERTICALLY AGAINST STERN WALL FOR TRANSPORT.
 - SEE A03 FOR FRAME DETAILS. SEE A04 SECTION B-B FOR SLOT CROSS-SECTION.

TRANSFORMATION SEQUENCE

SIDE ELEVATION – FOLD-OUT DEPLOYMENT (4 STEPS)

DEPLOYED PLAN VIEW

SCALE 1:12 – TOP DOWN

HINGE DETAIL

SCALE 1:2 – CROSS SECTION AT HINGE

HINGE SPECIFICATIONS

TYPE:	CONTINUOUS PIANO
MATERIAL:	304 STAINLESS STEEL
LEAF WIDTH:	1.5" (OPEN)
LENGTH:	72" CONTINUOUS
PIN DIA:	3/8"
LEAF THICK:	0.060"
QTY REQ'D:	2 (BOW + STERN)

DRAW LATCH DETAIL

SCALE 1:1 – OVER-CENTER MECHANISM

LATCH SPECIFICATIONS

TYPE:	OVER-CENTER DRAW
MATERIAL:	304 STAINLESS STEEL
HOLD FORCE:	600 LBF MIN
MOUNTING:	4× 1/4-20 BOLTS
QTY REQ'D:	8 TOTAL (4 PER SECTION)
PULL FORCE:	25 LBF TO RELEASE

FOLD-OUT FRAME

EXPLODED – 24"×96" PANEL FRAME

DRIVE-IN HYBRID DUCK BLIND

LITTORAL IRONCLAD SERIES

FOLD / FLOAT CONFIGURATION

FOLD-OUT DEPLOYMENT & HINGE DETAILS

SHEET:	A07 OF 12	DWG NO:	DIHDB-A07
SCALE:	AS NOTED	REV:	A
UNITS:	INCHES [IN]	DATE:	2026-03-06

MATERIAL NOTES

ALL FRAME: A500 GR-B STEEL
HINGES: 304 STAINLESS STEEL
LATCHES: 304 SS OVER-CENTER

TOLERANCES

FRAMING: +/- 1/16"
HINGE ALIGN: +/- 1/32"
ANGLES: +/- 0.5 DEG

GENERAL NOTES

- ALL WELDS PER AWS D1.1 UNLESS NOTED
- DEBURR ALL EDGES AND CORNERS
- PRIME AND PAINT ALL STEEL SURFACES
- FOLD-OUT PANELS TO LAY FLAT WITHIN 1/8" OF MAIN FRAME WHEN DEPLOYED

FOLD-OUT DATA

COMPACT: 12'×8' (TRANSPORT)
DEPLOYED: 16'×8' (FIELD)
DEPLOY TIME: < 2 MIN (2 PERSON)
HINGES: 2× PIANO 1.5"×72"
LATCHES: 8× OVER-CENTER DRAW

DROP LEG ASSEMBLY

SCALE 1:2 – TELESCOPING LEG DETAIL

CROSS SECTION

SCALE 2:1 – CUT THROUGH BOTH TUBES

PIN POSITION TABLE

POS	EXT.	GROUND CLR	USE
0	0"	0"	STOWED
1	6"	6"	SHALLOW
2	12"	12"	MEDIUM
3	18"	18"	DEEP
4	24"	24"	MAX

PIN: 1/2" DIA SPRING-LOADED
 DETENT: SPRING BALL, 5 LB PULL
 HOLES: 33/64" DIA (SLIP FIT)

SPRING PIN DETAIL

SCALE 2:1

4-LEG LAYOUT

SCALE 1:15 – UNDERSIDE PLAN VIEW

LEVELING PROCEDURE

SIDE ELEVATION – UNEVEN GROUND

MOUNTING BRACKET DETAIL

SCALE 1:1 – U-BRACKET ASSEMBLY

- BRACKET NOTES**
1. WELD BRACKET TO FRAME BEFORE ASSEMBLY
 2. BORE HOLE +1/8" OVERSIZE FOR CLEARANCE
 3. DEBURR ALL EDGES AFTER CUTTING

DRIVE-IN HYBRID DUCK BLIND

LITTORAL IRONCLAD SERIES

DROP LEGS & LEVELING

TELESCOPING SUPPORT LEGS & GROUND LEVELING SYSTEM

SHEET: A08 OF 12
 SCALE: AS NOTED
 UNITS: INCHES [IN]

DWG NO: DIHDB-A08
 REV: A
 DATE: 2026-03-06

LEG SPECIFICATIONS

OUTER: 2" x 2" x 0.120 A500 GR-B
 INNER: 1.5" x 1.5" x 0.120 A500 GR-B
 FOOT PAD: 6" DIA x 3/8" A36 PLATE

PERFORMANCE

MAX EXTENSION: 24"
 PIN POSITIONS: 5 (0-6-12-18-24")
 MAX SLOPE: 15 DEGREES

LOAD RATING

STATIC LOAD PER LEG: 1,500 LBF
 TOTAL CAPACITY (4 LEG): 6,000 LBF
 SAFETY FACTOR: 3:1
 MAX LATERAL LOAD: 500 LBF/LEG

GENERAL NOTES

1. ALL WELDS PER AWS D1.1
2. GREASE INNER TUBE BEFORE ASSEMBLY
3. USE ON FIRM GROUND ONLY; MUD/SAND REQUIRES ADDITIONAL PAD (8" x 8" MIN)
4. INSPECT PINS BEFORE EACH USE

PANEL LAYOUT – FLAT PATTERN

SCALE ~1:8 – ALL 8 CAMO PANEL ZONES

LEGEND

- GROMMET / ATTACHMENT POINT
- BRUSH HOLDER POCKET (2" PVC)
- CAMO FABRIC (600D POLYESTER)
- - CUTOUT / OPENING

PANEL ZONE MAP

MATERIAL SPECIFICATION

FABRIC: 600D POLYESTER, UV-RESISTANT
 PATTERN: REALTREE MAX-7 OR
 MOSSY OAK SHADOWGRASS
 GROMMETS: #4 BRASS, ROLLED RIM
 12" O.C. ALONG ALL EDGES
 SEAMS: DOUBLE-NEEDLE LOCK STITCH
 1" REINFORCED HEM ALL EDGES
 BRUSH POCKETS: 2" DIA x 6" DEEP
 SEWN TO TOP EDGE
 ATTACHMENT: 1" SPRING CLIPS + VELCRO

SIDE ELEVATION – PANELS INSTALLED

SCALE 1:12

ATTACHMENT DETAILS

SCALE 1:1

DETAIL A – SPRING CLIP 1:1 SCALE

DETAIL B – VELCRO STRAP 1:1 SCALE

DETAIL C – BRUSH HOLDER 1:1 SCALE

PANEL SCHEDULE

ZONE	PANEL ID	WIDTH	HEIGHT	MATERIAL	QTY	ATTACHMENT	WEIGHT	GROMMETS
PORT_FRONT	P1	72"	48"	600D POLY / RT MAX-7	1	CLIP + VELCRO	3.2 lb	20
PORT_REAR	P2	72"	48"	600D POLY / RT MAX-7	1	CLIP + VELCRO	3.2 lb	20
STBD_FRONT	S1	72"	48"	600D POLY / RT MAX-7	1	CLIP + VELCRO	3.2 lb	20
STBD_REAR	S2	72"	48"	600D POLY / RT MAX-7	1	CLIP + VELCRO	3.2 lb	20
BOW	B1	96"	48"	600D POLY / RT MAX-7	1	CLIP + VELCRO	4.3 lb	24
STERN	E2	96"	48"	600D POLY / RT MAX-7	1	CLIP + VELCRO	2.8 lb	18
ROOF_PORT	R1	144"	~54"	600D POLY / RT MAX-7	1	CLIP + VELCRO	7.2 lb	24
ROOF_STBD	R2	144"	~54"	600D POLY / RT MAX-7	1	CLIP + VELCRO	7.2 lb	24
TOTAL PANELS:					8	TOTAL WEIGHT:	34.3 lb	170

HARDWARE PER BLIND:

- 1" SPRING CLIPS: 96 EA (12 PER PANEL)
- 1" VELCRO STRAPS: 48 EA (6 PER PANEL)
- 2" PVC SLEEVES: ~56 EA (TOP RAIL PANELS ONLY)
- #4 BRASS GROMMETS: 170 EA

DRIVE-IN HYBRID DUCK BLIND CAMO PANEL SYSTEM

SHEET: A09 OF 12
 SCALE: AS NOTED
 DATE: 2026-03-06

REVISION: A – INITIAL RELEASE
 DRAWN BY: D. HAMPSON
 CHECKED: –

NOTES:

1. ALL PANELS 600D POLYESTER, UV-STABILIZED, WATER-RESISTANT COATING
2. PATTERN: REALTREE MAX-7 (PRIMARY) OR MOSSY OAK SHADOWGRASS (ALT)
3. ALL SEAMS DOUBLE-NEEDLE LOCK STITCH WITH BONDED NYLON THREAD
4. GROMMETS: #4 BRASS, ROLLED RIM, SET WITH GROMMET PRESS
5. BRUSH HOLDER POCKETS SEWN TO PANEL TOP EDGE, 12" O.C.
6. ALL PANELS REMOVABLE FOR SEASONAL STORAGE
7. STERN PANEL E2 HAS 52" x 48" CUTOUT FOR BOAT ENTRY SLOT
8. ROOF PANELS OVERLAP WALL PANELS BY 4" MIN AT EAVE LINE
9. INSTALL SPRING CLIPS FIRST, THEN SECURE WITH VELCRO STRAPS
10. TOTAL SYSTEM WEIGHT: ~34.3 LB (ALL 8 PANELS + HARDWARE)

REV	DATE	DESCRIPTION	BY
A	2026-03-06	INITIAL RELEASE – CAMO PANEL SYSTEM	DH

ENTRY RAMP DETAIL

SCALE 1:3 – 3/16" 6061-T6 ALUMINUM DIAMOND PLATE

ENTRY RAMP SPECIFICATIONS

MATERIAL:	3/16" 6061-T6 AL DIAMOND PLATE
DIMENSIONS:	36" L x 52" W
BENT LIPS:	1" ON 3 SIDES (L, R, LEADING)
HINGE:	SS PIANO HINGE, 36" x 2"
ANGLE:	~21° DEPLOYED
LOAD RATING:	500 LB UNIFORM LOAD
WEIGHT:	~18 LB
STOW METHOD:	FOLD UP AGAINST STERN WALL

SIDE STEP ASSEMBLY

SCALE 1:3 – FOLD-DOWN STEP DETAIL

STEP LOCATIONS

PORT SIDE: STA 4'-0" & STA 8'-0" FROM BOW
 STBD SIDE: STA 4'-0" & STA 8'-0" FROM BOW
 LOAD RATING: 300 LB PER STEP

PLATFORM CROSS-SECTION

SCALE 1:3 – THROUGH SIDE DECK

EDGE PROTECTION DETAIL

1:1 SCALE

- DECK SURFACE OPTIONS:
- GRIP-STRUT (PRIMARY)
 - PUNCHED DIAMOND PLATE
 - AL DIAMOND TREAD W/ ANTI-SLIP COATING

PLATFORM SPECIFICATIONS

DECK WIDTH:	22" PER SIDE
DECK LENGTH:	12'-0" (144") PER SIDE
SURFACE:	GRIP-STRUT GRATING
EDGE PROTECT:	10" KICK PLATE (14 GA)
LOAD RATING:	75 PSF (STANDING LOAD)
FRAME:	2"x2" TUBE CROSS-MEMBERS

PLATFORM PLAN VIEW

SCALE 1:16 – BOTH SIDE DECKS + STEP LOCATIONS

DRIVE-IN HYBRID DUCK BLIND RAMP & PLATFORM DETAILS

SHEET: A10 OF 12
 SCALE: AS NOTED
 DATE: 2026-03-06

REVISION: A – INITIAL RELEASE
 DRAWN BY: D. HAMPSON
 CHECKED: –

NOTES:

- ENTRY RAMP: 3/16" 6061-T6 ALUMINUM DIAMOND PLATE, 500 LB CAPACITY
- RAMP HINGES ON STAINLESS STEEL PIANO HINGE AT FLOOR EDGE
- RAMP STOWS VERTICALLY AGAINST STERN WALL – DRAW LATCH SECURES
- SIDE STEPS: EXPANDED METAL GRATING IN 1"x1" STEEL ANGLE FRAME
- STEPS FOLD UP AGAINST DECK EDGE WHEN NOT IN USE – PIN-LOCKED DEPLOYED
- SIDE DECK SURFACE: GRIP-STRUT OR PUNCHED DIAMOND PATTERN
- 10" KICK PLATE (14 GA STEEL) AT OUTBOARD EDGE OF ALL SIDE DECKS
- PLATFORM LOAD RATING: 75 PSF – SUITABLE FOR STANDING SHOOTERS
- ALL STEEL HOT-DIP GALVANIZED; ALL ALUMINUM MILL FINISH
- ALL NON-SLIP SURFACES TO MAINTAIN COEFFICIENT OF FRICTION > 0.50 WET
- SIDE DECK CROSS-MEMBERS: 2"x2"x0.120 A500 GR-B, 12" O.C.

REV	DATE	DESCRIPTION	BY
A	2026-03-06	INITIAL RELEASE – RAMP & PLATFORM DETAILS	DH

BILL OF MATERIALS

(ALL ITEMS)

#	DESCRIPTION	MATERIAL	SIZE	QTY	UNIT	TOTAL LEN	WT(LB)	SHEET
STRUCTURAL FRAME (A03)								
1	Floor perim. rail (long)	A500 Gr B	2"x2"x0.120" SQ	2	EA	144"	28.4	A03
2	Floor perim. rail (short)	A500 Gr B	2"x2"x0.120" SQ	2	EA	96"	18.9	A03
3	Floor X-member (full)	A500 Gr B	2"x2"x0.120" SQ	2	EA	96"	18.9	A03
4	Floor X-member (P/S)	A500 Gr B	2"x2"x0.120" SQ	10	EA	22"	21.7	A03
5	Boat slot rail (long)	A500 Gr B	2"x2"x0.120" SQ	2	EA	120"	23.6	A03
6	Wall stud (side walls)	A500 Gr B	2"x2"x0.120" SQ	12	EA	48"	56.9	A03
7	Wall stud (end walls)	A500 Gr B	2"x2"x0.120" SQ	8	EA	48"	37.9	A03
8	Top rail (long)	A500 Gr B	2"x2"x0.120" SQ	2	EA	144"	28.4	A03
9	Top rail (short)	A500 Gr B	2"x2"x0.120" SQ	2	EA	96"	18.9	A03
10	Ridge beam	A500 Gr B	2"x2"x0.120" SQ	1	EA	144"	14.2	A03
11	Roof rafter	A500 Gr B	2"x2"x0.120" SQ	6	EA	54"	32.0	A03
12	Corner gusset plate	A36	3/16" x 4"x4"	24	EA	---	5.8	A03
FOLD-OUT SYSTEM (A07)								
13	Fold-out frame rail (long)	A500 Gr B	2"x2"x0.120" SQ	4	EA	96"	37.9	A07
14	Fold-out frame rail (short)	A500 Gr B	2"x2"x0.120" SQ	4	EA	24"	9.5	A07
15	Fold-out cross-member	A500 Gr B	2"x2"x0.120" SQ	2	EA	96"	18.9	A07
16	Piano hinge (SS)	304 SS	1.5" wide x 72"	2	EA	---	4.0	A07
17	Over-center draw latch	Steel/zinc	---	8	EA	---	3.2	A07
OUTRIGGER SYSTEM (A05)								
18	Pedestal tube	A500 Gr B	2.5"x2.5"x0.188" SQ	4	EA	10"	12.8	A05
19	Outrigger arm	A500 Gr B	2"x2"x0.120" SQ	4	EA	48"	18.9	A05
20	Pedestal mount plate	A36	6"x6"x1/4"	4	EA	---	4.1	A05
21	Locking plate (round)	A36	5" dia x 3/16"	4	EA	---	1.2	A05
22	Foot plate	A36	8"x8"x1/4"	4	EA	---	8.7	A05
						SUBTOTAL (Items 1-22)	45.6	

#	DESCRIPTION	MATERIAL	SIZE	QTY	UNIT	TOTAL LEN	WT(LB)	SHEET
OUTRIGGER SYSTEM (A05) cont.								
23	Pivot pin (3/4" Gr 5)	Gr 5	3/4"x3.5"	4	EA	---	0.8	A05
24	Detent pin (spring)	Steel	3/8"	4	EA	---	0.4	A05
DROP LEG SYSTEM (A08)								
25	Drop leg outer tube	A500 Gr B	2"x2"x0.120" SQ	4	EA	14"	5.5	A08
26	Drop leg inner tube	A500 Gr B	1.5"x1.5"x0.120" SQ	4	EA	30"	8.7	A08
27	Mounting U-bracket	A36	3/16" bent	4	EA	---	3.2	A08
28	Foot pad (6" dia)	A36	6" dia x 3/8"	4	EA	---	3.0	A08
29	Locking pin (1/2" spring)	Steel	1/2"x5.5"	4	EA	---	0.6	A08
BOAT ENTRY (A06)								
30	Guide rail channel	A36	C3x4.1 x 120"	2	EA	---	82.0	A06
31	UHMW guide strip	UHMW-PE	3/4"x3"x120"	2	EA	---	6.0	A06
32	Entry ramp plate	6061-T6	3/16" x 36"x52"	1	EA	---	12.0	A06
33	Tie-down D-ring	Steel	1/2"	4	EA	---	1.6	A06
CAMO / MISC (A09, A10)								
34	Camo fabric panels	600D Poly	various	8	EA	~45 sq yd	18.0	A09
35	Spring clips (1")	Steel/zinc	1"	48	EA	---	2.4	A09
36	Brush holder PVC sleeve	PVC	2"x12"	24	EA	---	4.8	A09
37	Side step grating	Exp. metal	18"x36"	4	EA	---	24.0	A10
HITCH (A05)								
38	Tongue tube	A500 Gr B	2"x3"x0.120" rect	1	EA	42"	5.8	A05
39	Ball coupler (2")	Steel	7000 lb rated	1	EA	---	4.5	A05
40	Safety chain (3/8" Gr 43)	Gr 43	3/8" x 36"	2	EA	---	4.8	A05
41	Tongue jack	Steel	2000 lb	1	EA	---	8.0	A05
						SUBTOTAL (Items 23-41)	11.6	

BOM GRAND TOTAL (41 LINE ITEMS)

537.2 LBS

(excludes fasteners, weld consumables, paint)

NOTES:

- All steel tubing ASTM A500 Grade B, Fy = 46 ksi minimum.
- Plate steel ASTM A36, Fy = 36 ksi minimum.
- Weights are calculated values; actual may vary +/- 5%.
- All tubing dimensions are NOMINAL O.D. x wall thickness.

- "SQ" = square tube; "rect" = rectangular tube.
- UHMW-PE = Ultra-High Molecular Weight Polyethylene.
- Qty "—" in Total Length column = purchased item, not cut from stock.
- See Sheet A12 for weld symbols and connection details.

STEEL CUT LIST & NESTING DIAGRAM

(TUBE STOCK ONLY – 20 FT STICKS)

CUT #	TUBE SIZE	CUT LENGTH	QTY	ANGLE CUTS	BOM REF	TOTAL LIN.IN.	STOCK (20')
2" x 2" x 0.120" SQ TUBE (3.05 lb/ft)							
C-01	2"x2"x0.120"	144"	5	Square	#1,8,10	720"	3.0
C-02	2"x2"x0.120"	120"	2	Square	#5	240"	1.0
C-03	2"x2"x0.120"	96"	10	Square	#2,3,9,13,15	960"	4.0
C-04	2"x2"x0.120"	54"	6	Angle (roof pitch)	#11	324"	---
C-05	2"x2"x0.120"	48"	24	Square	#6,7,19	1152"	5.0
C-06	2"x2"x0.120"	24"	4	Square	#14	96"	---
C-07	2"x2"x0.120"	22"	10	Square	#4	220"	---
C-08	2"x2"x0.120"	14"	4	Square	#25	56"	---
2"x2" SUBTOTAL:						3768" (314 ft)	16 sticks
2.5" x 2.5" x 0.188" SQ TUBE (4.32 lb/ft)							
C-09	2.5"x2.5"x0.188"	10"	4	Square	#18	40"	1
2.5"x2.5" SUBTOTAL:						40" (3.3 ft)	1 stick
1.5" x 1.5" x 0.120" SQ TUBE (2.09 lb/ft)							
C-10	1.5"x1.5"x0.120"	30"	4	Square	#26	120"	1
1.5"x1.5" SUBTOTAL:						120" (10 ft)	1 stick
2" x 3" x 0.120" RECT TUBE (3.54 lb/ft)							
C-11	2"x3"x0.120"	42"	1	Square + fish mouth	#38	42"	1
CUT LIST TOTAL: 11 CUT TYPES 3970" (331 LIN FT) 19 STICKS (20 FT)							

NESTING DIAGRAMS (20 ft sticks, not to scale)

2"x2" STICK 1 of 16

144"	96"
------	-----

STICK 2

144"	96"
------	-----

STICK 3

144"	54"	W
------	-----	---

STICK 4

120"	120"
------	------

STICKS 5-8 (TYPICAL)

96"	96"	48"
-----	-----	-----

STICKS 9-13 (TYPICAL)

48"	48"	48"	48"	48"
-----	-----	-----	-----	-----

STICKS 14-16 (SHORTS + REMNANTS)

54"	54"	24"	24"	22"	14"	WASTE
-----	-----	-----	-----	-----	-----	-------

2.5"x2.5" STICK 1 of 1

200" REMNANT

1.5"x1.5" STICK 1 of 1

4x 30"	120" REMNANT
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2"x3" RECT STICK 1 of 1

42"	198" REMNANT
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= CUT PIECE

= WASTE / REMNANT

NOTE: Allow 1/8" kerf per cut. Remnants available for gussets and misc.

WEIGHT SUMMARY BY SUBSYSTEM

Structural Frame	420 lbs	(53.8%)
Boat Entry	102 lbs	(13.1%)
Fold-out System	73 lbs	(9.4%)
Camo / Misc	49 lbs	(6.3%)
Outrigger System	47 lbs	(6.0%)
Fasteners/Hardware	45 lbs	(5.8%)
Hitch	23 lbs	(2.9%)
Drop Leg System	21 lbs	(2.7%)

TOTAL DRY WEIGHT: ~780 LBS

Weight does not include occupants, decoys, ammunition, fuel, or natural vegetation.

Target tow weight (empty): 780 lbs
Recommended tow vehicle rating: 2000 lb min

HARDWARE SCHEDULE

BOLTS

TYPE	SPEC	QTY
3/8"-16 x 1" SHCS	Gr 8 / Zinc	20
1/4"-20 x 3/4" FHCS	Gr 5 / Zinc	40
3/8"-16 x 1.5" Hex	Gr 5 / Zinc	16
1/2"-13 x 2" Hex	Gr 5 / Zinc	8
5/16"-18 x 1" BHCS	18-8 SS	24

NUTS

3/8"-16 Nylock	Zinc	36
1/4"-20 Nylock	Zinc	40
1/2"-13 Nylock	Zinc	8
5/16"-18 Nylock	18-8 SS	24

WASHERS

3/8" Flat (SAE)	Zinc	72
1/4" Flat (SAE)	Zinc	80
1/2" Flat (SAE)	Zinc	16
5/16" Flat (SAE)	18-8 SS	48

CONSUMABLES

Weld wire ER70S-6 0.035"	~10 lbs
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COATING SCHEDULE

OPTION A: HOT DIP GALVANIZE

Per ASTM A123/A153
Min coating: 3.0 oz/sq ft
All fabrication complete before dip
Touch-up: zinc-rich cold galv spray

OPTION B: PAINT SYSTEM

- Sandblast to SSPC-SP6
- Zinc-rich primer (3.0 mil DFT)
- Epoxy intermediate (3.0 mil DFT)
- Polyurethane topcoat (2.0 mil)

Color: Flat OD Green or Marsh Tan
NOTE: Option A preferred for durability in saltwater/brackish environments.

DRIVE-IN HYBRID DUCK BLIND

SHEET A11 OF 12

MATERIAL SCHEDULE & CUT LIST

REV A

DWG: A11-MS-001

2026-03-06

DESIGNED: DH

CHECKED: ---

SCALE: N/A

EXPLODED ASSEMBLY VIEW

3/4 ISOMETRIC -- FRONT-RIGHT VIEWING ANGLE -- ALL ASSEMBLIES SEPARATED FOR CLARITY

SHEET INDEX

- A01 General Arr.
- A02 Elevations
- A03 Struct. Frame
- A04 Cross Sections
- A05 Pedestal/Hitch
- A06 Boat Entry
- A07 Fold/Float
- A08 Drop Legs
- A09 Camo Panels
- A10 Ramp/Platform
- A11 Material Sched.
- A12 EXPLODED ASSY

ASSEMBLY SEQUENCE

2 → 4 → 5 (WELD) → 3 → 1 → 6 → 7 → 8 → 9 → 11 → 10

VIEW NOT TO SCALE
SEPARATION GAPS FOR
ASSEMBLY CLARITY ONLY

ASSEMBLY KEY

#	ASSEMBLY	QTY	SHEET	FASTENERS	#	ASSEMBLY	QTY	SHEET	FASTENERS
①	Drop Leg Assy	4	A08	4x locking pins	⑦	Outrigger Arm	4	A05	4x pivot pin, 4x detent pin
②	Floor Frame	1	A03	Welded assembly	⑧	Entry Ramp	1	A06	1x piano hinge, 2x draw latch
③	Guide Rail + D-Rings	2+4	A06	20x 3/8" SHCS	⑨	Side Step	4	A10	8x hinge pins
④	Wall Frame	1	A03	Welded assembly	⑩	Camo Panel Set	8	A09	48x spring clips, Velcro
⑤	Roof Frame	1	A03	Welded assembly	⑪	Hitch Assembly	1	A05	4x 1/2" bolts
⑥	Fold-Out Section	2	A07	2x piano hinge, 8x draw latch					

NOTES:

1. ALL WELDED JOINTS PER AWS D1.1 STRUCTURAL WELDING CODE
2. APPLY PRIMER + ZINC COATING TO ALL STEEL AFTER FABRICATION
3. FIELD CONNECTIONS USE BOLTED OR PINNED FASTENERS ONLY

TOTAL ASSEMBLIES:

11 MAJOR ASSY GROUPS, 33 INDIVIDUAL COMPONENTS
EST. FIELD ASSEMBLY TIME: 4-6 HOURS (2 PERSONS)

DRIVE-IN HYBRID DUCK BLIND EXPLODED ASSEMBLY

SHEET A12 OF 12
2026-03-06

REV A
NOT TO SCALE